

A Case Study on Re-Cyclastic – A Move towards a Sustainable Future Develop a Corporate Plan

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ABSTRACT: The objective of the study was to develop a making a corporate plan which was sustainable and profitable. This involved study of what industry would be best which not only will be a good business opportunity but also support and preserve the environment in the process. Through the findings and study on various industries the report included a study of those companies which could be converted in producing less carbon or no carbon at all.

Exhibit I

Source:https://www.deccanherald.com/sites/dh/files/styles/article_detail/public/article_images/2019/08/15/file76nbneacphcnof6dox-1565814058.jpg?itok=vyIegEWX

CASE STUDY

Journey

During the conduct of research, it was found that 9.5 million ton of plastic is being produced annually, out of which 25,940 ton is being produced daily. In Delhi NCR region - alone produces 690 ton of plastic waste daily. Out of the 9.5 million ton of plastic produced annually only 4 million ton is being recycled and the rest 5.5 million ton of plastic is being disposed of in the landfills and ocean fills. This showcased to be very huge number which was being discarded.

To lessen the huge quantity of discarded plastic waste in the country a corporate plan was developed of how to recycle the plastic waste in an effective manner in the Delhi NCR region.

The foremost step of developing a corporate plan was:

- A. To identify the place of location and to plan where the factory setup would be
- B. To understand the sourcing and procurement of raw material i.e., plastic waste.

On Further analysis Agra was decided as the best location and the best place for the factory setup as it's close to the capital and other tourist places. This will also reduce the logistics cost and the customers of recyclastic were the auto parts manufacturing companies, beverage companies and the small scale FMCG industry. Towards procurement of raw materials identification of nearby local law authorities and local waste collectors as well as the law authorities of Delhi NCR – a tie up would be initiated. In addition it was also decided for the establishment of R.V.Ms (Reverse Vending Machines) in the residential societies, malls and other public areas. An awareness campaign would be rolled out to educate consumers through the use of waste collecting vehicles which will play the awareness message of disposing the plastic waste in the R.V.Ms and new type of special bins installed all over the cities.

Exhibit II

Source:https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&url=https%3A%2F%2Fubuntuu.com%2Fsolutions%2Fzeleno2&psig=AOvVaw05lrfAyb_NEsODgGLGqUQR&ust=1615307075010000&source=images&cd=vfe&ved=0CAIQjRxqFwoTCNDt2_WNoe8CFQAAAAAdAAAAABAD

The Corporate Plan would involve focusing on the products which has huge demand in the market such as PET bottles, fiber scrapes & polymers. It was decided that once the business grows they will later look at expansion. The way to measure the amount of plastic waste being recycled was to take the Material Flow Analysis – a step wise step approach which will be done during each quarter of the financial year to maintain the recycling process effectively and efficiently.

The overall cost of setup of plant is around Rs. 25 lakh. The cost of grinder is approximately Rs. 80,000. The Aglo costs the same as the grinder at Rs. 80,000. The granule maker with a capacity of 80kg – 500kg of plastic grinding is Rs. 6,20,000. The cost of electricity per month is Rs. 2-3 lakhs. The setup of infrastructure costs Rs. 8-10 lakhs. If you were to setup the plant away from natural source of ground water then the boring cost would be between 30-70 thousand depending upon the water level. Necessary permissions from the pollution control board would involve some fees. Procurement of machines such as weighing machine, sack sticher etc for Rs. 20,000 and some other miscellaneous expenses. Thus completing the overall cost of Rs. 25

lakh. The cost of land varies depending on whether the land is being purchased or it's being taken in lease and the location & accessibility to the raw material.

Further on the prices of the PET bottles were surveyed and it was decided to keep their prices relatively lower for effective market penetration and give additional perks to its customers if they ordered in bulk. The main selling point for their products will be the process of manufacturing these products and that its recycled plastic thus reducing waste. They also decided to manufacture their own products in the future and sell it in the market.

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